

Deepfake Image Detection Using ResNet50 and FPN Neural Networks

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Abstract— Until recently, the creation of hyper realistic fake content was limited to special effects experts, but now it has become increasingly accessible due to the advancements in AI and deep learning. This content is known as "deepfake" and the term originates from the combination of deep learning and fake, which refers to AI-generated synthetic media that uses two images, of both an impersonator and a target to create realistic looking forgeries. These forgeries are often used for malicious purposes, such as blackmail, harassment, damaging the reputation of a person or an organization, political interference, and spreading misinformation through social media. The continuous evolution of deep learning techniques, especially Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), has enhanced the ability to generate highly convincing synthetic media making detection really challenging just by normal human eyes. There exist various traditional methods for detection but they often struggle with complex and unseen data. The proposed methodology presents a deep learning-based approach to improve deepfake images detection, by leveraging Feature Pyramid Networks (FPN) and ResNet50. FPN is a neural network architecture that's well suited for detecting multiple scales that can be crucial for identifying large scale inconsistencies in deepfake videos, and ResNet50 is a deep convolutional neural network excels at identifying subtle spatial anomalies in images. By combining these two architectures we propose a model that can simultaneously analyze both global and local aspects of the content. This dual approach aims to surpass the traditional methods offering a more comprehensive system for identifying deepfake content across the social media. View this project on [Deepfake Image Detector](#).

Keywords— Deepfakes detections, Neural networks, Deep learning, Synthetic media, Feature Pyramid Networks, ResNet50, Social media manipulation.

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid growth of Artificial Intelligence and deep learning methods and technologies leads to new ways on how digital contents can be created and manipulated. Among these deepfake content have emerged as a concerning issue, bringing significant challenges to personal privacy and information integrity. This research paper proposes a dual architectural approach of Feature Pyramid Networks (FPN) and ResNet50 and utilizing their strength to address the growing threat posed by these synthetic media.

A. Background on deepfakes

Deepfake word comes from "deep learning" and "fake", these are AI generated synthetic media that mimics a real individual in images, videos, or audio. They are created using deep learning techniques like Generative Adversarial Networks (GAN). While originally this content was used for entertainment purposes it quickly took a turn for the worse and now are being misused raising serious concerns. Some of the potential threats includes manipulation, harassment, frauds etc.

That impact the society by undermining the trust in media, institutions, and individuals. These risks demand the urgent need for an effective solution to prevent deepfake related harm.
B. Current challenges in detection

There exist multiple traditional deepfake detection methodologies such as visual artifact analysis, temporal coherence examination, metadata scrutiny, and biological signal detection, but they are becoming increasingly ineffective as the technology advances. Modern deepfakes are able to replicate biological signals and maintain frame to frame consistency making the detection even more challenging. Moreover, the volume and variety of content circulating on social media pose significant challenge for timely and accurate detection.

C. Our Approach and its significance

To address the current limitations this research aims to use various deep learning-based approach for detection of deepfake images, combining Feature Pyramid Networks (FPN) and ResNet50 architectures. We believe this combination is well suited for this purpose as ResNet50 excels at identifying subtle spatial anomalies within images, and FPN allow multi scale feature extraction capabilities for anomaly detections. We would be testing this architecture on a dataset found on Kaggle that contains real and manipulated 256 X 256 face images. We have used multiple evaluation metrics like confusion matrix and obtained high accuracy and AUC scores using this approach. By integrating these two powerful architectures we aim to build a comprehensive image detection system.

This research will help towards contributing to the ongoing effort to fight the misinformation being spread in the form of images. We focus this work towards enhancing the detection accuracy, adapting to evolving threats, and promoting digital literacy. This research also impacts cybersecurity, digital forensics, and media studies by preserving authenticity towards digital age.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Deepfake Generation and Detection: A Benchmark and Survey, DOI: [arXiv:2403.17881v4](https://arxiv.org/abs/2403.17881v4). (Gan Pei, 2024)

The deepfake technology is driven by advancement in deep learning is evolving significantly, enabling the creation of highly realistic synthetic media. Techniques like Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) and Variational autoencoder were early techniques in the field of deepfake generation by providing frameworks for face swapping, face reenactment, and

talking face generation. However, diffusion models are also becoming a problem and a powerful alternative offering improved stability and quality in generating deepfake contents. The application of these models in creating these synthetic media has expanded across various domains, including entertainment, security, and malicious activities raising multiple ethical concerns.

As deepfake generation becomes more complex, the need for detection mechanism also grows. Early detection methods relied on handcrafted features, but the modern approaches are utilizing deep learning techniques, among these neural networks have played significant roles especially CNN and RNN. These models are used to identify subtle visual and temporal inconsistencies in deepfakes. Hybrid detection models combining multiple strategies have also been developed to address the increasing complexity of deepfake videos, especially those created using multiple step diffusion process. FaceForensics++ and deepfake detection challenge, have played major roles in evaluations and detection methods.

B. DEEPFAKES WITHOUT SEEING ANY, DOI: arXiv:2311.01458v1. (Tal Reiss, 2023)

Deepfake detection has become major research focus due to the rise of deep learning generative models that are able to produce realistic synthetic media. The traditional detection methods rely heavily on supervised learning techniques, where the detection models are trained on existing deepfakes. These models are effective against known deepfake techniques, but these models struggle to generalizing zero-day attacks, which involves novel or unseen manipulations. Approaches like artifact detection, which identify subtle inconsistency left by generative model are often bypassed as model architecture evolve. Additionally supervised learning can overfit to specific types to deepfakes, which results in limiting their adaptability.

Recent advancement in fact checking based detection approaches the issue differently. The concept of fake news detection has been adapted to deepfake detection by verifying the similarity between media content and associated claims. (Tal Reiss, 2023) introduced an approach named FACTOR, leveraging fact checking without needing any training on fake data. Unlike the traditional methods this method generalizes well to zero-day attacks by using off the shelf feature encoder to detect inconsistency in the claims that includes identity and audio-visual matching with respect to media, this approach takes a significant step in fighting against deepfake threats.

C. An Analysis of Recent Advances in Deepfake Image Detection in an Evolving Threat Landscape, DOI: arXiv:2404.16212v1. (Sifat Muhammad Abdullah, 2024)

The rise of deepfake images generated through sophisticated deep learning models, has raised significantly which concerns the integrity of online content, several state-of-the-art (SOTA) detection methods have been developed to reduce this growing threat, which have achieved some promising results that are available publicly. Early approach of detecting deepfakes were primarily focused on identifying images with the help of supervised learning. For instance,

methods that analyse texture statistics, frequency spectra, and local patches have been widely adopted, and showcasing high accuracy rates in controlled environments. Despite this the recent advancements and developments in generative models still pose considerable challenge to existing detections methods.

The ease access of generative AI technologies has encouraged the customization of models, such as Stable Diffusion and GANs, with widely expands the threat landscape. The problem rises, as the prior detection methods trained on limited generative model variant, struggle to generalize well with these custom models. Furthermore, the start of vision foundation models, which are large scale, pre-trained models such as CLIP and ViT, adds another layer of complexity. Attackers can exploit these models to generative adversarial deepfakes that bypass traditional detection methods without compromising image quality. The current researches need novel detection frameworks, focusing on content-agnostic features, ensemble modelling, and adversarial training to improve robustness against these evolving threats.

D. Deep fake detection and classification using error-level analysis and deep learning. DOI: 10.1038/s41598-023-34629-3. (Rimsha Rafique, 2023)

The rapid increase of deepfakes has started this sudden need for extensive research into deepfake detection methods, with recent studies in hybrid approach's in combining multiple techniques. Error level analysis is a forensic method for identifying image tampering through compression artifact analysis, and it has displayed promising results in detecting manipulated images. Simultaneously Convolution Neural Networks (CNN) have emerged as a powerful tool for automatic feature extraction in image analysis. Some popular architecture such as GoogLeNet, ResNet, and SqueezeNet have demonstrated high efficiency and accuracy in various computer vision tasks, including deepfake detection.

Recent researches have explored integration of ELA with deep learning techniques to enhance detection accuracy. For instance, researchers have proposed a framework combining ELA with CNN- extracted features, showing better results compared to single method approaches. Furthermore, transfer learning using pre trained CNN for feature extraction, followed by classification with traditional machine learning algorithms such as Support Vector Machines and K-Nearest Neighbours (KNN), has shown significant results. The development and evaluation of these methods are backed by datasets like Yonsei University Computational Intelligence and Photography Lab dataset, FaceForensic++, and DeepFake Detection Challenge dataset, which provides diverse collection of real and manipulated images and videos.

E. Detecting Deepfake Images Using Deep Learning Techniques and Explainable AI Methods. DOI: 10.32604/iasc.2023.029653. (Wahidul Hasan Abir, 2022)

With the recent advancements in deepfake technology there are significant concerns being raised towards the authenticity of

social and digital media, leading researchers to develop robust deepfake detection methods. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have played a huge role in developing powerful tools for solving these issues. For instance, Nguyen et al. used VGC architecture with SRM filter layers to highlight image noise features, achieving 85.7% accuracy on the Celeb-DF dataset. Similarly, Guera and Delp utilized CNN algorithms for feature extractions from video frames, implementing InceptionV3 and ResNet50 to attain 91.56% accuracy in deepfake video detection.

These approaches display effectiveness if deep learning in deepfake detections, the inherent "black-box" nature of these models carry challenges in terms of interpretability and trustworthiness. Addressing this issue (MT Ribeiro, 2016) introduced Model-Agnostic interpretability explanations (LIME) algorithm, which helped out in various field for its ability to explain individual predictions of any machine learning model. However, its application and reliability in the deepfake detection domain still remains unexplored.

The current study builds on the foundations of these CNN models by combining them with LIME for the detection. By using pre trained models such as InceptionResNetV2, DenseNet201, InceptionV3, and ResNet152V2, and applying LIME for result interpretation, this research aims to improve upon the detection accuracy and model explainability. The approach seeks to improve upon the accuracy levels and address the critical need for transparency in the AI systems used for sensitive applications like deepfake detection.

F. A Machine Learning based Approach for DeepFake Detection in Social Media through Key Video Frame Extraction. DOI: 10.1007/s42979-021-00495-x. (Alakananda Mitra, 2021)

Deepfake detection has attracted much attention in recent times due to growing advancements in AI and deep learning especially in AI-generated video and image manipulation techniques, particularly in social media. Several researches have leveraged convolutional neural networks (CNNs) to detect forgery traces through facial expression and moments, among these a work that stands out is by (Andreas Rössler, 2019) who introduced the FaceForensics++ dataset and demonstrated the efficiency of deep CNN models such as Xception which was used to identify forged video content. The approaches which were based on a recurrent neural networks (RNNs) named as Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks, this focused on temporal inconsistencies across frames, as outlined by (Sabir, 2019). The study primarily focuses on spatial and temporal features extraction to improve the detection across datasets.

Apart from all this the models using transfer learning techniques such as ResNet50 and InceptionV3, have shown promising results by reducing extensive labelled data. Researchers applied CNN based models to compress videos, enhancing detection efficiency in real time social media application. Despite all this the need for lightweight and efficient models for mobile devices remains largely unexplored. The recent works are focusing on reducing the computational power and costs by frame section techniques

and improving accuracy by utilizing the architectures like depth wise separable convolution. The paper contributes by addressing these gaps offering neural network-based models optimized for real time detection.

G. AI DEEP FAKE DETECTION RESEARCH PAPER, DOI: IJNRD2310407. (Raghava M S, 2023)

There has been a significant evolution with the rise of advance deep learning algorithms, focusing in the field of Generative Adversarial Network (GAN's) and Autoencoders. Just a decade ago (Ian J. Goodfellow, 2014) introduced GANs, which laid out the foundation for generative synthetic media, that includes realistic images and videos that are difficult to differentiate from real content. According to various studies GAN were especially good at face swapping, lip sync, and puppet master techniques. Techniques such as Face2Face and Deep Video Portraits leverage GANs to manipulate facial expression and moments, that also helps in real time modifications. Researchers like (Tero Karras, 2019) with StyleGAN demonstrated the ability to create highly realistic faces, pushing the capabilities of deepfake generations. This development raised significant risk for the misuse of technologies for malicious purposes and raise the need for solid detection mechanisms.

On the other hand, multiple significant efforts have been taken to counter the deepfake threat using various neural networks techniques such as Convolution neural networks (CNNs), Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), and hybrid models. Studies by (Darius Afchar, 2018) have proposed the use of Mesonet that focuses on detecting artifact in deepfake videos by analysing the inconsistency in facial textures. Similarly, a work by (Lingzhi Li, 2020) introduces Face X-ray to identify mixing artifacts between source and target faces. Other researches are exploring the effectiveness of various models like ResNet and Xception to classify deepfakes with high accuracy. The challenges in such as generalization to new and unseen deepfakes techniques, as well as adversarial attacks on detection system still remains. The ongoing researches are finding ways to improve both generative and detection methodologies for deepfakes with a goal to maintain integrity and privacy across various media platforms.

III. OBJECTIVES

To achieve a robust deepfake detection mechanism we aim to achieve some of the following objectives:

A. Enhanced Detection Accuracy

We are aiming to develop a dual architectural model combining ResNet50 and Feature Pyramid Networks (FPN) to achieve higher accuracy in deepfake image detection compared to single architectural model.

B. Superior Model Performance

We are aiming to design a model that outperforms traditional deepfakes models in terms of metrics such as accuracy and speed. Leveraging the strength of neural network architecture will provide us spatial anomaly detection and multi-scale feature analysis to create a more robust system.

C. Generalization to Unseen Data

Making sure the model maintains consistent performance when faced with new data that has not been seen previously during model training. Implementing diverse training data and data augmentation techniques so that the model will have ability to generalize well.

D. Multi-scale Analysis Capability

Develop the model ability to detect deepfake artifacts at various scales within the images, from fine details to large *structural inconsistencies*. Utilize FPN architecture to efficiently capture and analyse features at different resolution.

E. Real-time Processing for Social Media Applications

Optimizing the model architecture and implementation to get a real time processing capability suitable for high volume social environment. Aiming to balance accuracy and speed for practical deployment in real world scenarios.

IV. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

Here are all the modules that were incorporated during the development of this project. We have explained all the steps taken and also provided the architecture and working of this project.

A. System Overview

Developed a deepfake detection system that utilizes deep learning approach that utilizes ResNet50 and Feature Pyramid Networks (FPN) to analyze image and classify them as real or fake.

- **Data Ingestion:** The project loads images from the provided dataset that contains real and fake human/people face images.
- **Preprocessing:** The data is preprocessed and resized to 224 x 224 pixel and normalized using mean and standard deviation.
- **Feature Extraction:** ResNet50 model is used to remove the final classification layer and extract features from input images.
- **Multi-scale Feature Analysis:** FPN takes the feature from different levels of ResNet50 and create feature pyramids to analyze images at multiple scales.
- **Classification:** Multi-scaled features are processed by additional convolution layer and a final fully connected to classify images as binary values of 0 (real) or 1 (fake).
- **Training:** The model is finally trained with cross entropy loss and Adam optimizer for deepfake detection.
- **Evaluation:** The model is finally checked on different performance metrics like accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and ROC AUC.

B. Dataset Description

The dataset used in the development of this project is downloaded from Kaggle (deepfake and real images). The dataset originally belongs to OpenForensics (Echizen, 2021). The dataset contains 256 x 256 jpg format images that contains images of human faces that are both real and fake.

The dataset comes in an extracted format and when unzipped it contains 3 folders named as Test, Train, and Validation. All these 3 folders contain 2 additional folders named Real and Fake and this folder contains the images that

is later used for training and testing the model and finally validating it.

C. Dataset Preprocessing

The data preprocessing is an important step to prepare images for input into the deep learning model. This stage involves various steps:

- **Image Resizing and Normalization:** All the images are resized to 224 x 224 pixel considering it's the standard input size for many models. After resizing images are normalized using mean and standard deviation, this helps in standardizing the input data that leads to faster convergence during training. The preprocessing is implemented using torchvision transform.
- **Data Loading and Batching:** We used a custom class (`torch.utils.data.Dataset`). The class is responsible for loading images and apply preprocess transformation. Furthermore, the data is loaded into batches using PyTorch's that helped in efficient batching, shuffling, and parallel data loading.
- **Train and Test Split:** The take the custom dataset that was prepared in previous step and perform a split to organize data in separate directories. This make sures there is no data leakage during the evaluation process.

D. Model Architecture

The projects works on a dual architecture utilizing ResNet50 and Feature pyramid network. We have described how both models work and discussed about the custom layer and modifications:

- **ResNet50:** It's a deep convolution neural network architecture that trains very deep networks and use residual connections effectively. It contains 50 layers organized into five stages, each having multiple convolutional layers followed by batch normalization and ReLU activation. We used the pre trained model for removing the final average pooling and fully connected layers which helps, which allow us to extract hierarchical features from the images, capturing low-level details and high-level relevant information.
- **Feature Pyramid network:** It's an architecture that's designed for multiscale feature extraction. It creates a pyramid by combining low resolution with high resolution. The FPN takes different features from ResNet50 and create consistent number of channels across all scales, this allows model to analyze deepfake at multiple scales.
- **Custom layer Modifications:** We added several custom layer processes to multiscale features. These layer process the FNP output by combining information across scales for final classification.

E. Training Process

We use various techniques and functions to train our model, here are the step-by-step processes we took:

- **Loss function:** We use binary cross entropy loss for our classification task.
- **Optimizer:** We use Adam optimizer for its adaptive learning rate and properties.
- **Learning Rate:** We set the learning rate as 0.001, but other values could be tested or used too like 0.9 etc.
- **Setting epoch and batch size:** We set the epoch size to

TABLE I

Requirements for deepfake detection model

Hardware Requirements	Software Requirements
<p>Graphic Card (Recommended):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - NVIDIA GPU with CUDA support (Nvidia 1050Ti or above). <p>Compute Resources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 8 core CPU. - Adequate RAM (16GB or above) <p>Storage:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SSD with at least 100GB free space <p>Network Infrastructure:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High-speed Internet Connection. 	<p>Operating System:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Windows 10/11, macOS, or Linux (Ubuntu 18.04 or later recommended) <p>Deep Learning Framework:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PyTorch: 1.7.0 or later - torchvision (Compatible version with PyTorch) <p>CUDA Toolkit:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Version compatible with PyTorch and GPU <p>Necessary Library:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - numpy - scikit-learn - Pillow (PIL) - matplotlib - seaborn - pandas <p>Development Tools:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Anaconda - Jupyter Notebook

^a These are the general requirements.

10 meaning the model will go through ten rounds of training and the batch size as 32.

- Training and validation: We set a loop so the training data iterates over dataset 10 times and after each round model will computer prediction and loss. After the model is trained it will be evaluated on the validation set to check its performance.

F. Evaluation Metrics

We use several metrics to evaluate and get a better understanding of how our model is performing:

TP = True Positives
 TN = True Negatives
 FP = False Positives
 FN = False Negatives

- Accuracy: Ratio of correct prediction by total number of cases.

$$\frac{(TP + TN)}{(TP + TN + FP + FN)} \quad (1)$$

- Precision: Ratio of correct positive prediction by total number of positive cases.

$$TP / (TP + FP) \quad (2)$$

- Recall: Ratio of correct positive prediction by all actual positive observations.

$$TP / (TP + FN) \quad (3)$$

- F1-score: The harmonic mean of Precision and Recall.

$$\frac{2 * (Precision * Recall)}{(Precision + Recall)} \quad (4)$$

- Specificity: Ratio of correctly predicted negative observations to by actual negative observations.

$$TN / (TN + FP) \quad (5)$$

- ROC AUC: summarizes how well a classifier can distinguish between positive and negative classes.

Fig. 1. Workflow diagram for deepfake detection model.

Fig. 2. Architecture of deepfake detection model.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Checking how the model performs is a critical part to help us understand how well the detection model is predicting. We can check the performance of the model using various metrics:

A. Model Performance Metrics

Accuracy: 0.9074
 Precision: 0.8860
 Recall (Sensitivity): 0.9366
 F1-score: 0.9106
 Specificity: 0.8777
 ROC AUC: 0.9714

Fig. 3. Model performance metrics.

Our model demonstrates an overall strong performance in deepfake detection. We manage to achieve accuracy of 90.74% indicating the reliability for detection of real and fake images. The recall value of 93.66% suggests the model's effectiveness in identifying large proportion of deepfake images. This is important as in real world analysis minimizing false negatives (undetected deepfakes) is prioritized.

B. ROC Curve Analysis

Fig. 4. Models ROC curve

The ROC curve shows us the model's discriminative ability across various thresholds with the AUC score of 0.9714, suggesting our model shows excellent capability in distinguishing between real and fake images. This AUC score also tells us that the model maintains good performance even when the decision threshold is adjusted, providing good flexibility in real world deployments.

C. Confusion Matrix Interpretation

The confusion matrix is providing us insights about the types of error model makes. For our detection model:

- True Positive = 4751
- False Positive = 662
- False Negative = 348
- True Negative = 5144

Fig. 5. Confusion Matrix

These values are finally used to calculate the accuracy of our model and we can see that there is a good balance of True positive and True Negative.

D. Error Analysis

Analyzing misclassified images reveals pattern in our model's weakness.

Fig. 5. Image displays model detected False Positive

Fig. 5. Image displays model detected False Negative

This analysis suggests the area for potential improvements in prediction such as analyzing blurred images, handling low lights images etc.

E. Implications and Applications

The High performance of our model can be useful and have significant implication for:

- Social media: We can use this potentially for automated screening of uploaded content.
- Digital Forensics: Assisting in verifications of tampered content or digital evidences.
- Media Literacy: Developing and enhancing tools to help public identify potential deepfakes.

VI. FUTURE WORKS

While our deepfake detection model demonstrates strong performance, there is always room for improvement and expansion that can be adopted as the technologies grow:

A. Handling diverse image: The current model may not work well with blurry and low light images. We will add images with wide range of qualities and implement adaptive preprocessing techniques to enhance low quality inputs.

B. Extension to Animated images: Current model is limited to static image analysis. Later we will extend the architecture to process short video clips and GIFs.

C. Robustness to Advanced Manipulation: As the technologies evolve, we must adapt to new techniques as well for detection. In future development working on explainable AI techniques to provide insight into the model's decision-making process can turn out very useful.

D. Real-time Detection and Scalability: Working on model compression techniques will help us in efficient deployment on devices and applications. Furthermore, developing a framework for large scale media analysis will help organizations to detect and stop and label content as deepfake.

VII. CONCLUSION

This paper projected an approach to develop a deepfake image detector, by combining the ResNet50 and Feature Pyramid Networks. The primary objective of this project was to develop a detection model capable for identifying tampered and manipulated images being circulated over the internet and social media. We manage to develop a model that is able to perform multi-scale analysis and find inconsistencies in images.

Our proposed model achieved a great performance metrics of 90.74% and a recall of 93.66% demonstrating its effectiveness in detecting deepfake images. The ROC-AUC score of 0.9714 further underscores the model's strong discriminative ability across various classification threshold.

Our approach contributes to the ongoing efforts to fight the spread of misinformation over the internet through manipulated media. In conclusion, this work is a step forward in deepfake detection technologies, offering a foundation upon which future improvements can be done. As the amount of digital manipulation evolves so must our methods for detecting and reducing those harms.

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